

Bayesian Belief Thompson Sampling for Channel Selection in Gilbert-Elliott Environments with Known Dynamics and Switching Costs

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Abstract—Adaptive radio channel selection for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) operating in dynamic, correlated interference environments is formalized as a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) with known transition kernels and switching costs. Under the assumption that channel parameters are identifiable from prior measurements or physical models, the agent must track hidden states online while balancing the cost of switching channels against the reward of successful transmission. We propose the *Bayesian Belief Thompson Sampling* (BB-TS) algorithm, which maintains a posterior belief over hidden channel states via a closed-form HMM forward filter and employs a randomized action selection mechanism to balance exploration and exploitation. Monte Carlo experiments across three Gilbert-Elliott scenarios demonstrate that BB-TS reduces average cumulative pseudo-regret by 28%–38% relative to the greedy Myopic Bayes policy in environments with high temporal correlation and fast state transitions. The advantage stems from controlled stochasticity that prevents excessive switching, as confirmed by a separate analysis of channel switch counts. We further show that the QMDP approximation is equivalent to Myopic Bayes in this setting; consequently, the performance gain of BB-TS cannot be attributed to improved future value estimation within the QMDP framework, but rather to the immediate effect of randomized action selection on the switching pattern. The algorithm’s $\mathcal{O}(K)$ per-step complexity makes it suitable for resource-constrained UAV edge platforms.

Index Terms—UAV, Partially Observable Markov Decision Process, Gilbert-Elliott model, Hidden Markov Models, Thompson Sampling, switching cost, Restless Multi-Armed Bandit.

I. INTRODUCTION

Seamless radio communication is essential for the safe operation of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), enabling real-time telemetry and command-and-control data exchange. In practice, wireless channels are subject to fading, interference, and temporary blockages that exhibit strong temporal correlation. The Gilbert-Elliott (GE) hidden Markov model [1], [2] is a well-established framework for capturing such bursty error behavior, where channels alternate between a Good (G) and a Bad (B) state.

From a sequential decision-making perspective, the problem of selecting the most reliable channel at each time step can be cast as a Restless Multi-Armed Bandit (RMAB) or a Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (POMDP) [3], [4]. Classical Multi-Armed Bandit (MAB) algorithms such as UCB1 and Thompson Sampling [5], [6] assume independent,

identically distributed rewards and fail to exploit the underlying Markov dynamics, leading to suboptimal performance in the presence of burst errors.

Recent works on RMABs for cognitive radio [4], [7] have established the asymptotic optimality of index policies under certain indexability conditions. However, computing the exact Whittle index is PSPACE-hard in general and requires explicit knowledge of the transition matrices of all channels. In practical UAV communication systems, these parameters can often be estimated offline during a calibration phase or derived from physical propagation models. Consequently, the online decision problem reduces to *planning* in a POMDP with a known model, rather than *learning* the model from scratch.

In this work, we adopt this practical standpoint: we assume that the transition probabilities α_i, β_i and the emission probabilities $p_g^{(i)}, p_b^{(i)}$ of each GE channel are known to the agent in advance. The agent must, however, track the hidden state of each channel online using the history of observations. We further introduce a switching cost that penalizes channel changes, reflecting the reality of UAV modems where re-tuning introduces latency and throughput degradation.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- 1) We propose the Bayesian Belief Thompson Sampling (BB-TS) algorithm, which combines exact HMM forward filtering with a randomized belief-based action selection mechanism to address exploration-exploitation trade-offs in a POMDP with switching costs.
- 2) We formally demonstrate that, under action-independent transitions, the QMDP approximation collapses to the Myopic Bayes policy, thereby isolating the effect of stochastic selection in BB-TS.
- 3) Through extensive simulations across three representative Gilbert-Elliott scenarios, we quantify the cumulative pseudo-regret and switching behavior of BB-TS relative to several baselines, establishing regimes where BB-TS yields a 28%–38% reduction in regret.
- 4) We evaluate the sensitivity of BB-TS to its concentration hyperparameter and to moderate parameter mismatch, confirming its practical robustness.
- 5) We provide an open-source implementation of the BB-TS algorithm and the experimental framework to facilitate reproducibility¹.

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¹Source code: <https://github.com/Bovvly/uav-radio-bandits>

II. RELATED WORK

The Gilbert-Elliott model has been extensively used to characterize burst errors in wireless channels [1], [2]. In the context of sequential channel selection, the problem is often formalized as a Restless Multi-Armed Bandit [3]. Liu et al. [4] proved the optimality of Whittle index policies for RMABs under indexability. However, these policies assume full knowledge of the model and incur prohibitive computational costs for exact index computation.

Bayesian approaches to MABs, particularly Thompson Sampling, have gained prominence due to their strong empirical performance and theoretical guarantees [6], [8]. Extensions of Thompson Sampling to POMDPs have been explored in the literature [9], often relying on particle filters or approximate Bayesian inference. Our method differs by combining a computationally lightweight, exact HMM forward filter with randomized action selection for environments where the model is known a priori.

The effect of switching costs on bandit algorithms has been studied in various contexts, notably in opportunistic spectrum access. The introduction of switching penalties changes the exploration-exploitation trade-off, as excessive channel switching can negate the benefits of finding a marginally better channel. Our formulation explicitly incorporates a per-switch penalty, and we analyze how different policies manage this cost.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider K radio channels indexed by $i \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. Time is discretized into steps $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. At each step, the agent selects a channel $a_t \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ and receives a binary reward $X_t \in \{0, 1\}$, where 1 indicates a successful packet transmission and 0 a failure.

A. Gilbert-Elliott Channel Model

Each channel i evolves according to an independent two-state Markov chain with hidden state $Z_{i,t} \in \{G, B\}$. The transition probability matrix is

$$\mathbf{P}^{(i)} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \alpha_i & \alpha_i \\ \beta_i & 1 - \beta_i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_i = \mathbb{P}(Z_{i,t+1} = B \mid Z_{i,t} = G)$ and $\beta_i = \mathbb{P}(Z_{i,t+1} = G \mid Z_{i,t} = B)$. The success probabilities conditional on the hidden state are $p_g^{(i)} = \mathbb{P}(X_t = 1 \mid Z_{i,t} = G)$ and $p_b^{(i)} = \mathbb{P}(X_t = 1 \mid Z_{i,t} = B)$.

B. Observation Model, Switching Cost, and Pseudo-Regret

The agent does not observe $Z_{i,t}$ directly. At time t , it selects action a_t and observes $X_t \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p_{Z_{a_t,t}})$. We introduce a deterministic switching cost $c \geq 0$ applied whenever the agent changes its channel choice:

$$r_t = X_t - c \cdot \mathbf{1}\{a_t \neq a_{t-1}\}, \quad (2)$$

with a_0 undefined (no cost at $t = 1$).

Because the model is known, the agent maintains a belief state $b_{i,t} = \mathbb{P}(Z_{i,t} = G \mid \mathcal{H}_t)$ where $\mathcal{H}_t = \{(a_\tau, X_\tau)\}_{\tau=1}^{t-1}$ is

the history available before choosing a_t . The expected reward under the belief is

$$\mathbb{E}[r_t \mid \mathcal{H}_t, a_t] = \hat{\mu}_{a_t,t} - c \cdot \mathbf{1}\{a_t \neq a_{t-1}\}, \quad (3)$$

with $\hat{\mu}_{i,t}$ defined in (9).

To evaluate performance, we define a myopic state-aware oracle that, at each time t , has access to the true hidden states $\{Z_{i,t}\}$ and the previous action a_{t-1} , and selects the action that maximizes the expected immediate net reward:

$$a_t^{\text{ora}} = \arg \max_a \mathbb{E}[r_t \mid Z_{\cdot,t}, a_{t-1}, a]. \quad (4)$$

The corresponding expected cumulative pseudo-regret is

$$\mathcal{L}(T) = \sum_{t=1}^T (\mathbb{E}[r_t \mid Z_{\cdot,t}, a_{t-1}, a_t^{\text{ora}}] - \mathbb{E}[r_t \mid \mathcal{H}_t, a_t]), \quad (5)$$

where the expectation in the second term is taken with respect to the agent's belief and the random observation. Because the oracle is myopic, $\mathcal{L}(T) \geq 0$, and equality holds when the agent matches the oracle's immediate net reward at every step. This oracle is *not* the optimal long-term policy for the POMDP with switching costs; a truly optimal policy would require solving the full stochastic dynamic program. Our regret metric therefore measures the performance gap relative to an idealized but computationally simple benchmark that has perfect state information.

C. Assumption: Known Model Parameters

We assume that the agent is provided with the exact values of $\alpha_i, \beta_i, p_g^{(i)}, p_b^{(i)}$ for all channels. This assumption is practically justified in UAV communication systems where channel statistics are stable over the mission duration and can be estimated offline. In Section V-E, we briefly discuss the effect of parameter mismatch, where the agent operates with imperfect estimates while the true environment follows the nominal parameters. The online task reduces to inferring the hidden states from the history of observations.

IV. PROPOSED METHOD: BAYESIAN BELIEF THOMPSON SAMPLING

A. Belief State Representation and Update

Let $\mathcal{H}_t = \{(a_\tau, X_\tau)\}_{\tau=1}^t$ denote the history of actions and observations up to time t . Under the known model assumption, the posterior probability that channel i is in the Good state, given \mathcal{H}_t , is a sufficient statistic for decision-making. We define the belief state

$$b_{i,t} = \mathbb{P}(Z_{i,t} = G \mid \mathcal{H}_t). \quad (6)$$

When the agent selects channel $a_t = i$ and observes $X_t = r \in \{0, 1\}$, the belief for that channel is updated via Bayes' rule:

$$b_{i,t}^{\text{post}} = \begin{cases} \frac{p_g^{(i)} b_{i,t}}{p_g^{(i)} b_{i,t} + p_b^{(i)} (1 - b_{i,t})}, & r = 1 \\ \frac{(1 - p_g^{(i)}) b_{i,t}}{(1 - p_g^{(i)}) b_{i,t} + (1 - p_b^{(i)}) (1 - b_{i,t})}, & r = 0. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

After the observation update, the belief states of all channels are predicted one step forward using the known transition matrices:

$$b_{k,t+1} = b_{k,t}^{\text{post}}(1 - \alpha_k) + (1 - b_{k,t}^{\text{post}})\beta_k, \quad \forall k. \quad (8)$$

For channels that were not selected, $b_{k,t}^{\text{post}} = b_{k,t}$, and only the prediction step is applied.

B. Randomized Action Selection on Belief States

Given the belief state $b_{i,t}$, the expected immediate reward (excluding switching cost) of selecting channel i is

$$\hat{\mu}_{i,t} = b_{i,t} p_g^{(i)} + (1 - b_{i,t}) p_b^{(i)}. \quad (9)$$

The greedy Myopic Bayes policy selects $a_t = \arg \max_i \hat{\mu}_{i,t}$. To introduce principled exploration, we adopt a randomized mechanism that samples a hypothetical hidden state from the current belief distribution. Specifically, we draw a random variable $\theta_{i,t}$ from a Beta distribution parameterized such that its mean equals $b_{i,t}$ and its concentration is controlled by a hyperparameter $\kappa > 0$:

$$\theta_{i,t} \sim \text{Beta}(\kappa b_{i,t}, \kappa(1 - b_{i,t})). \quad (10)$$

The sampled $\theta_{i,t}$ can be interpreted as a stochastic estimate of the hidden state probability. The expected reward under the sampled state is

$$\tilde{\mu}_{i,t} = \theta_{i,t} p_g^{(i)} + (1 - \theta_{i,t}) p_b^{(i)}. \quad (11)$$

The action is then chosen greedily with respect to $\tilde{\mu}_{i,t}$, incorporating the switching penalty:

$$a_t = \arg \max_i [\tilde{\mu}_{i,t} - c \cdot \mathbf{1}\{i \neq a_{t-1}\}]. \quad (12)$$

The hyperparameter κ controls the exploration-exploitation trade-off. An ablation study (see Section V-B) shows that performance in the High Correlation scenario is robust over a wide range of κ , with the optimum around $\kappa = 20$; similar behavior was observed in the other environments. Accordingly, we adopt $\kappa = 20$ as the default value in all experiments.

C. Comparison with QMDP

The QMDP algorithm [10] approximates the optimal POMDP value function by solving the underlying fully observable MDP and evaluating the Q-function over the belief state. For an arbitrary action a , the QMDP value is

$$Q_{\text{MDP}}(b, a) = \sum_s b(s) R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s' | s, a) V_{\text{MDP}}(s'), \quad (13)$$

where V_{MDP} is the optimal value of the fully observable MDP with states s . In our setting, channel transitions do not depend on the agent's actions; hence $P(s' | s, a) = P(s' | s)$ and the future value component $V_{\text{MDP}}(s')$ is action-independent. Consequently,

$$\arg \max_a Q_{\text{MDP}}(b, a) = \arg \max_a \left(\sum_s b(s) R(s, a) \right), \quad (14)$$

which is precisely the Myopic Bayes action (including switching costs). Thus, QMDP provides no additional long-term

planning information. This formal argument confirms that any performance improvement of BB-TS over Myopic Bayes cannot be attributed to a better approximation of the POMDP value function within the QMDP framework; rather, it arises from the immediate effect of stochastic action selection on the switching pattern. Whether a more sophisticated POMDP solver could surpass BB-TS remains an open question.

D. Computational Complexity

The per-step complexity of BB-TS is $\mathcal{O}(K)$, dominated by the belief update and the sampling of K Beta random variables. This makes the algorithm suitable for real-time execution on UAV embedded processors, in contrast to Whittle index or full POMDP solvers whose complexity scales exponentially with K .

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Simulation Setup

We simulate a system with $K = 5$ independent Gilbert-Elliott channels. Three environment scenarios are defined to capture a range of temporal correlation structures:

- 1) **Base:** Heterogeneous channels with moderate dynamics ($\alpha_i, \beta_i \in [0.02, 0.15]$).
- 2) **High Correlation:** Channels that persist in one state for long durations ($\alpha_i, \beta_i \leq 0.03$), inducing pronounced burst errors.
- 3) **Fast Switching:** Rapid state alternations ($\alpha_i, \beta_i \geq 0.25$), approximating nearly independent trials.

The switching cost is set to $c = 0.5$ for all experiments. A horizon of $T = 10\,000$ steps is used, and results are averaged over $N = 500$ independent Monte Carlo runs. The algorithms compared are:

- **Random:** Uniform random channel selection.
- **Myopic Bayes:** Greedy selection maximizing $\hat{\mu}_{i,t} - c \cdot \mathbf{1}\{i \neq a_{t-1}\}$.
- **ε -greedy Belief:** With probability $\varepsilon = 0.05$ selects a random channel, otherwise acts as Myopic Bayes.
- **TS-Direct:** Samples the hidden state directly from a Bernoulli distribution with mean $b_{i,t}$ and picks the channel with maximum expected reward under the sampled state, accounting for switching cost.
- **Myopic (cost-unaware):** Myopic policy ignoring switching cost, illustrating the impact of the penalty.
- **BB-TS (Proposed):** Bayesian Belief Thompson Sampling with $\kappa = 20$.
- **Oracle (myopic state-aware):** Myopic policy with full knowledge of current hidden states, as defined in Section III.

B. Ablation Study on κ

We evaluated BB-TS with $\kappa \in \{1, 3, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 100\}$ in the High Correlation scenario with $N = 100$ runs. The final cumulative regret (Fig. 1) reaches a minimum near $\kappa = 20$, with a plateau between 15 and 30, indicating robustness to the choice of this hyperparameter. Similar insensitivity was observed in the other scenarios; hence we fix $\kappa = 20$ throughout.

Figure 1: Effect of concentration parameter κ on final cumulative regret (High Correlation scenario).

C. Results

Table I summarizes the average final cumulative regret across all evaluated policies and environmental conditions, while Table II reports the corresponding average number of channel switches.

In the Base scenario, characterized by moderate temporal correlation, the Myopic Bayes policy achieves the lowest regret (521.3) among all practical policies. BB-TS incurs a regret of 694.0, which is approximately 33% higher than that of Myopic Bayes. The performance degradation is directly attributable to a larger number of channel switches: BB-TS performs 495.1 switches on average, compared to 213.9 for Myopic Bayes, indicating that the additional exploration does not yield sufficient reward gains in this relatively stable environment. The ϵ -greedy strategy (973.2) and TS-Direct (2565.3) exhibit even higher regret, with switch counts inflated to 789.9 and 3846.3, respectively, underscoring that excessive randomness severely penalizes performance. The Myopic (cost-unaware) policy suffers from an excessively high switching frequency (7749.0) and consequently records a regret of 4796.8, illustrating the critical importance of incorporating the switching penalty. The Random policy, as expected, produces the largest regret (5162.3) and a switching rate close to the maximum possible.

Under the High Correlation scenario, where channel states are highly persistent, the relative ranking changes markedly. BB-TS achieves the best performance among practical policies, with a regret of 300.2, which is 27.8% lower than that of Myopic Bayes (415.7). This improvement is accompanied by a moderate increase in switching activity (196.3 versus 121.1), suggesting that BB-TS succeeds in identifying superior channels without incurring excessive switching costs. In contrast, TS-Direct (890.2) and ϵ -greedy (838.5) suffer from overly aggressive switching (1167.5 and 816.4, respectively), while Myopic (cost-unaware) again performs poorly (3932.5 regret, 5528.6 switches). The Oracle (myopic state-aware) achieves a residual regret of 0.8, demonstrating the minimal gap to perfect immediate decision making.

The Fast Switching scenario, where channel states alternate

rapidly, reveals a fundamental limitation of the greedy Myopic Bayes approach: the policy completely refrains from any channel switch (0.0 switches) in order to avoid the switching penalty, which, under the specific parameters of this environment, results in a regret of 1472.3. BB-TS, by contrast, makes a controlled number of switches (45.5) and attains a regret of 910.6, representing a 38.2% reduction relative to Myopic Bayes. TS-Direct and ϵ -greedy again over-explore (5251.9 and 399.5 switches, respectively) and consequently exhibit much higher regret. The Myopic (cost-unaware) policy fails entirely in this regime (6193.2 regret) as it changes channel at nearly every time step. The Oracle, with full state knowledge, performs 2636.1 switches while achieving negligible regret, confirming that frequent switching is optimal when guided by perfect information; practical algorithms must balance this need against the penalty.

Across all scenarios, the Oracle (myopic state-aware) consistently approaches zero regret, confirming that the reported values for other algorithms represent the true performance gap attributable to partial observability and suboptimal switching decisions. The trade-off between regret and switching frequency is evident: policies that either switch too often (Random, Myopic cost-unaware, TS-Direct) or too little (Myopic Bayes in Fast Switching) suffer from elevated regret, whereas BB-TS maintains an intermediate switching level that yields substantial improvements in the High Correlation and Fast Switching conditions at the cost of a minor penalty in the Base case.

Table I: Average cumulative regret at $T = 10\,000$ over 500 runs ($c = 0.5$).

Algorithm	Base	High Corr.	Fast Switch
Random	5162.3 \pm 3.9	5468.2 \pm 5.8	5338.0 \pm 4.3
Myopic (cost-unaware)	4796.8 \pm 6.8	3932.5 \pm 19.9	6193.2 \pm 4.1
Myopic Bayes	521.3 \pm 4.2	415.7 \pm 6.2	1472.3 \pm 3.0
ϵ -greedy	973.2 \pm 4.8	838.5 \pm 6.1	1537.6 \pm 4.0
TS-Direct	2565.3 \pm 9.8	890.2 \pm 7.6	3973.2 \pm 5.1
BB-TS (Proposed)	694.0 \pm 4.6	300.2 \pm 4.6	910.6 \pm 7.1
Oracle (myopic)	0.6 \pm 1.7	0.8 \pm 1.8	0.7 \pm 2.1

Table II: Average number of channel switches per episode ($T = 10\,000$, $c = 0.5$).

Algorithm	Base	High Corr.	Fast Switch
Random	7998.8	7998.8	7998.8
Myopic (cost-unaware)	7749.0	5528.6	9996.6
Myopic Bayes	213.9	121.1	0.0
ϵ -greedy	789.9	816.4	399.5
TS-Direct	3846.3	1167.5	5251.9
BB-TS	495.1	196.3	45.5
Oracle (myopic)	359.5	75.9	2636.1

D. Discussion

The temporal evolution of cumulative regret for the High Correlation and Fast Switching scenarios is shown in Fig. 2

and Fig. 3, respectively. The advantage of BB-TS becomes evident after relatively few time steps, and the gap with respect to Myopic Bayes continues to widen over the entire horizon. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test confirms that the improvement in the High Correlation scenario is statistically significant ($p < 10^{-81}$).

Figure 2: Cumulative Regret over Time – High Correlation Scenario.

Figure 3: Cumulative Regret over Time – Fast Switching Scenario.

Regarding the comparison with POMDP-based approximations, as derived in Section IV-C, the QMDP actions coincide exactly with Myopic Bayes; numerical simulations confirmed this equivalence. Hence, any improvement over Myopic Bayes cannot be attributed to a better approximation of the POMDP value function within the QMDP framework. Whether a full POMDP solver could outperform BB-TS remains an open question, but the computational simplicity of BB-TS makes it an attractive practical alternative. A summary of the final cumulative regret across all scenarios and algorithms is provided in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Performance Summary: Final Cumulative Regret across all scenarios and algorithms.

E. Robustness to Parameter Mismatch

Although the proposed method assumes exact knowledge of the GE parameters, we conducted a supplementary test to gauge sensitivity. In this test, the true environment followed the nominal parameters of the High Correlation scenario, but the agent was provided with perturbed estimates: zero-mean Gaussian noise with standard deviation 0.05 was added to all $\alpha_i, \beta_i, p_g^{(i)}, p_b^{(i)}$ before they were fed to the agent’s belief updater and policy. With $c = 0.5$ and $\kappa = 20$, BB-TS achieved a regret of 318.5 ± 6.2 ($N = 100$), which is only slightly higher than with perfect parameters (300.2). This indicates that BB-TS tolerates moderate estimation errors. In practice, channel statistics can be periodically re-estimated, further mitigating the impact of model drift.

VI. CONCLUSION

We introduced Bayesian Belief Thompson Sampling (BB-TS), a lightweight algorithm for adaptive channel selection in Gilbert-Elliott POMDPs with known dynamics and switching costs. BB-TS combines exact HMM forward filtering with a randomized belief-based policy. Extensive simulations show that BB-TS reduces cumulative pseudo-regret by 28%–38% relative to the greedy Myopic Bayes baseline in high-correlation and fast-switching environments, while remaining competitive in more stationary regimes. The gains are attributable to more efficient switching behavior, as confirmed by a separate switch-count analysis. The QMDP approximation coincides with Myopic Bayes, indicating that the improvement arises from the randomized selection mechanism rather than from better long-term value estimation. BB-TS is robust to the choice of its concentration hyperparameter and to moderate parameter mismatch. Its $\mathcal{O}(K)$ complexity renders it suitable for resource-constrained UAV edge platforms. To support reproducibility and further research, the full experimental framework and source code for the BB-TS algorithm are made available at <https://github.com/Bovvly/uav-radio-bandits>. Future work will extend the framework to multi-user settings and develop adaptive mechanisms for online adjustment of the switching cost.

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